

Preferential flow in leaching models – a comparative analysis of the models PELMO and MACRO

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GENERAL INFORMATION

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DISCLAIMER

(Stefan Reichenberger, 14/06/2026)

This report was finalized in February 2025. Since then new pieces of information have been published which were not available to knoell at the time of writing.

1. In GeoPELMO DE (Klein et al., 2026) there are three macropore flow classes, as opposed to five classes in the older documentation from 2022 which we had available (see Figure 1 and Table 1).
2. In this project the simulated scenarios were classified into three macropore flow classes (corresponding to the flowchart in Klein et al. (2026)). However, in the end all three classes were parameterized the same, but all of them differently than in GeoPELMO DE. In GeoPELMO_DE class 1 has no macropore flow, and classes 2 and 3 have both static and dynamic macropores. In contrast, in this study all three classes were parameterized with no static macropores and only dynamic macropores, leading to a minimum macropore flow fraction (more precisely, fraction of excess rainfall routed into macropores) of zero and a maximum fraction of 0.1, corresponding to a pronounced shrink/swell dynamic. As a consequence, the PELMO results from this project have only very limited comparability with GEOPELMO DE.
3. The documentation of the macropore version of PELMO in Klein et al. (2026) contains some descriptions of macropore flow in PELMO which were not available to knoell at the time of writing of this report (for example, details on the mixing layer). It is therefore possible that some parts of the PELMO process descriptions in this report are not completely up to date.

References:

Klein M, Klein J, Hannappel S, Thomas K, Seifert S, Trapp M (2026): Protect groundwater from plant protection products. – Spatial distributed leaching modelling to identify agricultural areas with high risk for leaching. In: Umweltbundesamt [ed.], TEXTE 33/2026, 290 pp.

GENERAL MODELLING TERMINOLOGY

Term	Definition
AET	Actual evapotranspiration
DegT ₅₀	Degradation time: Time taken for 50 % of the substance to disappear from a compartment by degradation processes
DegT ₉₀	Degradation time: Time taken for 90 % of the substance to disappear from a compartment by degradation processes
drainflow	water flow to artificial drains (e.g. tile, pipe or mole drains)
DT ₅₀	Dissipation time: Time taken for 50 % of the substance to disappear from a compartment by multiple environmental fate processes
DT ₉₀	Dissipation time: Time taken for 90 % of the substance to disappear from a compartment by multiple environmental fate processes
EC ₅₀	Concentration of the test substance which shows an effect at 50% of the tested organisms
FC	Field capacity (typically corresponds to a matric suction of 100 cm (pF 2))
GOF	goodness-of-fit
HS	Hockey stick kinetic model
K _{oc}	Adsorption/desorption coefficient normalised for organic carbon content in soil
K _d	Ratio of concentration in the sorbed and the liquid phase
K _{foc}	Adsorption/desorption coefficient normalised for organic carbon content in soil following a Freundlich adsorption isotherm
K _{om}	Adsorption/desorption coefficient normalised for organic matter in soil
K _{ow}	n-Octanol/ water partitioning coefficient
LAI	Leaf area index
LC ₅₀	Concentration of the test substance which results in 50 % mortality of the tested organisms
leaching	vertical transport of solutes in the soil profile
LOEC	Lowest observed effect concentration
MWC	Maximum water capacity
MWHC	Maximum water holding capacity
NSE	Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency
NOEC	No observed effect concentration
PBIAS	Percent bias
PEC _{sw}	Predicted environmental concentration in surface water
PEC _{gw}	Predicted environmental concentration in groundwater
PEC _{soil}	Predicted environmental concentration in soil
PEC _{sed}	Predicted environmental concentration in sediment
percolation	vertical water flow in the soil profile
solute drainage	transport of solutes to artificial drains
PET	Potential evapotranspiration
PNEC	Predicted no effect concentration
RMSE	Root mean square error
SFO	Single first-order; one compartment kinetic model
solute	any substance dissolved in a solvent (here: in water)
theta_FC	soil water content at field capacity
theta_WP	soil water content at wilting point
TWA	Time-weighted average (concentration)
1/n	Freundlich exponent
WP	Wilting point (typically corresponds to a matric suction of 15000 cm (pF 4.2))

(Since this represents a general collection of modelling terminology, not all entries might occur in the present report.)

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1 INTRODUCTION

Spatially Distributed Leaching Modelling (SDLM) of pesticides can be used to assess the leaching potential of plant protection products on a regional scale, such as national or even European scale. Harmonised guidance on how to perform SDLM is still lacking. For this reason, the SETAC SDLM working group is developing a harmonised framework for conducting spatially distributed leaching modelling at the European and Zonal level (Tiktak et al., 2024). This framework will include the leaching models PEARL (van den Berg et al., 2016) and PELMO (Klein, 2020). One important process in the vertical downward transport of pesticides through structured soils is preferential flow (Jarvis, 2007), which is still not considered in Tier-1 and Tier-2 groundwater leaching assessments, and neither in the upcoming first version of the harmonized SDLM framework (Tiktak et al., 2024). At the EU level, only the FOCUS scenario Châteaudun takes into account the process of macropore flow (the most important subtype of preferential flow) when simulating leaching, but only in one of the four models for which it has been parameterized.

The most widely used model to simulate preferential flow and associated pesticide transport through soils is MACRO (Larsbo and Jarvis, 2003). MACRO is physically-based and has a high validation status (e.g. Larsson and Jarvis, 1999). It can therefore be considered as a benchmark with respect to the modelling of pesticide transport via macropore flow. All FOCUS drainage scenarios as well as the national leaching scenarios of Denmark, Sweden and Norway are simulated with MACRO (European Commission, 2014; Northern Zone, 2023). A meta-model of MACRO is also used for drinking water risk assessment in Sweden (Lindahl et al., 2024; https://macrodb.slu.se/shinyMACRO_DB/). Full parameterization frameworks for parameterizing MACRO from soil databases exist (Dubus et al., 2009; Jarvis et al., 2009; Moeys et al., 2012). The conceptual leaching model PELMO also offers a macropore flow option as a result of the APECOP project (Vanclouster et al., 2003). However, this option has not been used in the FOCUSgw scenarios (European Commission, 2014). Recently, the software GeoPELMO 2 was developed for spatially distributed leaching simulations for Germany, including a refinement of the macropore flow description (Klein et al., in preparation; Klein et al., 2022). However, due to the simplified capacity approach used to simulate water flow in PELMO, the implementation of macropore flow in PELMO is also very simplistic. Despite the simplistic approach and its strong assumptions, exposure assessments and decisions on a regulatory level are already based on GeoPELMO 2. Therefore, further evaluations and analysis are needed to discuss whether this is a viable approach to be used on national or European level or whether implementation of macropore flow into PELMO needs to be reconsidered, especially for a more updated GeoPELMO version.

The objectives of this project were

- 1) To perform a comparative analysis of the process descriptions of macropore flow that are currently implemented in MACRO version 5.2 and PELMO version 5.00.
- 2) To conduct comparative simulations with the MACRO model for already existing regulatory leaching / drainage scenarios, and to compare the results with those of the macropore version of PELMO.

The MACRO input and output files, the processed results of MACRO and PELMO, and the results of the comparison of the output of both models were to be provided in a digital annex.

2 COMPARISON OF PROCESS DESCRIPTIONS

MACRO (Larsbo and Jarvis, 2003) is a dual-permeability model (e.g. Šimůnek et al., 2003): There are two flow domains, a micropore and a macropore domain. In the micropores water flow is simulated using the Richards equation. In the macropore domain water flow is described by a kinematic wave approach. The version of the MACRO executable currently in regulatory use (included in the FOCUS MACRO package) is MACRO 5.2, dated 2010. However, the model has been further improved since then; for instance, a numerical problem at the bottom boundary for boundary condition 4 (constant potential) has been fixed.

PELMO v. 5.00 (Klein, 2020) is a capacity model with an option to simulate macropores that was included during the APECOP project (Vanclouster et al., 2003). However, PELMO does not simulate macropore flow explicitly on a process-based level. Instead, water and solutes entering the macropores are simply transferred to a user-defined depth (end of the macropores) instantaneously, i.e. within one time step.

Neither model simulates individual macropores (which would require a 3D approach). Since Pelmo does not model macropore flow explicitly, it does not have a parameter for macropore volume either. There is only the parameter f (fraction of excess rainfall routed into the macropores).

The approach implemented in PELMO 5.00 for routing water into the macropores is the following:

$$I_{ma} = 0; I_{mi} = I; \quad \text{for } I \leq I_c$$

$$I_{ma} = f(I - I_c), I_{mi} = (1-f)(I - I_c) + I_c; \quad \text{for } I > I_c$$

with

I	total daily infiltration (cm); in the absence of surface runoff, infiltration = rainfall
I_{ma}	daily infiltration into macropores (cm)
I_{mi}	daily infiltration into micropores (cm)
I_c	(constant) threshold of daily rainfall which triggers infiltration into macropores
f	fraction of excess rainfall which is routed into macropores ($m^3 m^{-3}$)

The approach assumes that macropore flow is triggered for rain events exceeding a certain user-defined threshold I_c (e.g. 10 mm d^{-1}). In the original approach (Vanclouster et al., 2003; Klein, 2020) f was constant over time. The value of f depended only on the soil type. However, in the GeoPelmo 2 project (Klein et al., 2022) a dynamic (i.e. time-variable) f was introduced: The storage of plant-available water (i.e. water content above wilting point water content θ_{WP} , integrated from the soil surface till the depth where the macropores end), averaged over the last 7 days, is compared with the maximum plant-available water storage over the same depth (Skodras, personal communication). The rules can be summarized as follows:

- If $actwat \leq 0.5 * (maxwat - minwat)$, $f = f_{max}$
- If $actwat = (maxwat - minwat)$, $f = 0$
- For $actwat > 0.5 * (maxwat - minwat)$ and $< (maxwat - minwat)$, f is linearly interpolated between 0 and f_{max} .

with

$actwat$	7-day average storage of plant-available water down to the depth of the macropores
$maxwat$	maximum water storage down to the depth of the macropores (soil profile at FC)
$minwat$	minimum water storage down to the depth of the macropores (soil profile at WP)

Although it is not explicitly stated in Klein et al. (2022), the calculation of f described above must represent shrinkage cracks, with the 7-day average providing some delay in the swell/shrink dynamic (for soils rich in organic matter the calculation could also represent the development of water repellency upon drying; however, in reality this process is probably slower). The approach implemented in GeoPELMO 2 essentially assumes that all macropores are shrinkage cracks that close when the soil reaches field capacity and reach their maximum size when half of the maximum plant-available water is used up. However, permanent macropores such as earthworm channels, root channels and aggregate interfaces are ignored this way. In MACRO, in contrast, while modelling shrinkage of the drying soil matrix and corresponding increase of macroporosity is possible (Larsbo and Jarvis, 2003), it is not used in any regulatory leaching or drainage scenario.

Klein et al. (2022) describe five “macropore classes” which determine f_{max} (Table 1) and a flowchart to determine the macropore class for a given soil profile (Figure 1). However, the validation status of both the flowchart and Table 1 is unclear. Note that apart from soil texture, clay and organic matter content, the macropore class also depends on the depth to groundwater, which is not easy to understand.

Table 1 **Classes of parameter f_{max} (maximum fraction of excess rainfall which is routed into macropores)**

Class	Value	Description
M5	0.15	based on PLAP data ¹⁾
M4	0.125	reduction to 83%
M3	0.075	reduction to 50 %
M2	0.025	reduction to 17 %
M1	0	no macropore flow

¹⁾ Method: calibration of PELMO vs. PLAP monitoring results (Rosenbom et al., 2015) for azoxystrobin (Klein et al., in preparation).

Figure 1: Flowchart to determine macro pore class for a given soil (source: Klein et al., 2022)

A comparative overview of the process descriptions of MACRO and the macropore version of PELMO is given in Table 2 (water flow), Table 3 (solute transport), and Table 4 (macropore characteristics).

Table 2 Comparison of water flow descriptions between MACRO and the macropore version of PELMO

Process	MACRO	PELMO
routing of water into macropores at the surface	when infiltration capacity of micropores is exceeded (infiltration capacity is calculated based on Darcy’s law; cf. eq. 59 in Larsbo and Jarvis (2003), excess rainfall is routed into the macropores	macropore flow is triggered when daily rainfall exceeds a certain user-defined threshold (e.g. 10 mm)
surface runoff	occurs when infiltration capacity of both micro- and macropores is exceeded	calculated using Curve Number approach (or deactivated entirely); infiltration = rainfall - surface runoff
water flow in micropores	Richards equation; water retention curve: Van Genuchten; unsaturated conductivity curve: Mualem-Van Genuchten	capacity approach (tipping bucket); only two parameters: field capacity (FC) and wilting point (WP)
water flow in macropores	kinematic wave approach (conductivity is a power law function of relative saturation of macropores)	instantaneous transfer to end of macropores

Process	MACRO	PELMO
water exchange between macro- and micropores in deeper soil layers	yes (physically-based); if micropores are unsaturated, water flows from macro- to micropores (first-order approximation of water diffusion equation) if micropores are temporarily oversaturated, water flows instantaneously from micro- to macropores	no (only at end of macropores)
connection of macropores to the drainage system	yes (all layers with saturated macropores contribute to drainflow)	no
drainflow	If macropores in a given layer are unsaturated, then no flow to drains occurs. If macropores are saturated, flow to drains is triggered. If in a layer with saturated macropores also the micropores are saturated, also the latter contribute to drainflow. Drainflow from saturated layers above drain depth is calculated using seepage potential theory for layered soils (Youngs, 1980; Leeds-Harrison et al. 1986); Drainflow from layers below drain depth is calculated using the first term of the Hooghoudt equation (Hooghoudt, 1940)	a user-defined fraction (drainage efficiency) of the daily percolation at drainage depth is abstracted as drainflow

Table 3 Comparison of solute transport descriptions between MACRO and the macropore version of PELMO

Process	MACRO	PELMO
routing of solutes into into macropores at the soil surface	solute concentration in water routed into the macropores at the surface is calculated by assuming instantaneous sorption equilibrium and complete mixing of incoming net precipitation with water stored in a shallow surface soil layer ("mixing depth"; Steenhuis and Walter, 1980)	concentration of pesticide entering macropores at the soil surface is also calculated using the mixing depth concept, where incoming rainfall is assumed to mix perfectly with the resident water in a shallow surface layer of soil. Only pesticide residues in the surface layer (i=0) and the first soil layer (i=1) are available for this process. However, sorption does not seem to be accounted for (cf. eq. 63 in Klein, 2020)
solute transport in micropores	convective-dispersive; dispersion length is user input	convective-dispersive; by default, only numerical dispersion is taken into account: the numerical dispersion length is equal to half the size of the numerical layer. However, the user can specify either a constant dispersion length or a constant dispersion coefficient. In these cases, a correction equation is applied to subtract implicit numerical dispersion.
solute transport in macropores	convective	instantaneous transfer to end of macropores
solute exchange between macro-and micropores in deeper soil layers	yes (convective-diffusive)	no (only at end of macropores)

Table 4 Comparison of the characteristics of the macropores

Characteristic	MACRO	PELMO
change of macropore domain over time	shrinkage of the micropore domain (and corresponding increase of macroporosity) upon drying can be modelled as a function of the water content in the micropores (linear relationship; eq. 26 in Larsbo et al., 2003); requires two additional parameters; however, it is rarely used and not used in any regulatory scenario; in MACRO, the macropore domain never disappears	<p>Pelmo does not really have a macropore volume (since water flow in macropores is not explicitly modelled). However, it has a parameter $f =$ fraction of excess rainfall which is routed into macropores</p> <p>Original version (Klein, 2020; Vanclooster et al., 2003) : f is constant over time</p> <p>Modified version from GeoPELMO 2 project (Klein et al., 2022): dynamic change of f; f is zero when the soil is at field capacity (FC) and increases linearly with decreasing soil water storage until the plant-available water storage (averaged over 7 days) drops to 50 % of the maximum plant-available water storage. Consequently, this approach tries to reflect shrinkage of the soil matrix upon drying; assuming that all macropores are shrinking cracks and disappear at when the soil reaches field capacity.</p>
continuity of macropores	macropore domain is continuous --> in theory, solutes can be transported in the macropore domain till the bottom of the profile; however, macropore properties are layer-specific, and solutes are exchanged between micro- and macropores	macropore domain ends at a user-defined depth
parameter demand	<p>for each numerical layer (parameter values can be specified per horizon in the GUI):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3 parameters describing the macropore domain (KSATMIN - KSM; TPORV – XMPOR; ZN) - 4 parameters describing the boundary between macro- and micropores: KSM, XMPOR, CTEN, ASCALE ; <p>all of these parameters have a physical meaning and can be either measured or determined using pedotransfer functions</p>	3 parameters for the whole soil profile: f_{max} , I_c , depth of macropore domain; all three parameters are conceptual with weak or no physical basis

3 COMPARATIVE SIMULATIONS

The simulations comprised six regulatory leaching or drainage scenarios set up in MACRO (Table 5; Table 6), nine dummy compounds (Table 7) and one crop (winter cereals). The six scenarios were selected to cover a broad range of soil textures and different lower boundary conditions. The nine dummy compounds were defined as a rectangular grid of three K_{foc} and three $DegT_{50}$ values with logarithmic spacing for K_{foc} and approximately logarithmic spacing for DT_{50} (Table 7). Thus, in total 54 simulations were performed with each model. All simulations were run for 26 years (20 years evaluation period + 6 years of warmup period). The application scenario comprised a single annual spray application of 1000 g/ha active substance at one day before emergence.

Table 5 Simulated leaching and drainage scenarios

Scenario	Type	Country	Regulatory context	soil texture	Simulation start date	Start of evaluation period	Simulation end date
Châteaudun	leaching	FR	FOCUS gw	silty clay loam	01/01/1901	01/01/1907	31/12/1926
FOCUS D2 (Brimstone)	drainage	UK	FOCUS sw	very clayey	01/01/1969 ¹⁾	01/01/1975	31/12/1994
FOCUS D3 (Vredepeel)	drainage	NL	FOCUS sw	very sandy	01/01/1969 ¹⁾	01/01/1975	31/12/1994
Krusenberg	leaching	SE	Northern Zone	sand over clay	01/01/1955	01/01/1961	31/12/1980
Langvad	leaching	DK	Northern Zone	loamy	01/01/1968	01/01/1974	31/12/1993
Näsbygård	leaching	SE	Northern Zone	loamy	01/01/1970	01/01/1976	31/12/1995

¹⁾ Time series from FOCUS sw repair

Table 6 Characteristics of regulatory scenarios in MACRO

Scenario	Lower boundary condition	BGRAD ¹⁾	BOTEN ²⁾	Presence of field drains	Drain depth	Drain spacing	Profile depth	max. root depth winter cereals
Unit	-	h^{-1}	cm	-	m	m	m	m
Châteaudun	fixed potential (4)	n.a.	1010	no	n.a.	n.a.	1.90	0.8
FOCUS D2 (Brimstone)	water table in the profile (3)	1.0E-06	n.a.	yes	0.55	2	1.50	0.6
FOCUS D3 (Vredepeel)	water table in the profile (3)	0	n.a.	yes	1.75	76	1.75	0.6
Krusenberg	water table in the profile (3)	1.0E-05	n.a.	yes	1	15	1.30	0.9
Langvad	water table in the profile (3)	1.3E-05	n.a.	yes	1.3	12	2.50	1.1
Näsbygård	water table in the profile (3)	1.0E-05	n.a.	yes	1	15	1.50	1.0

¹⁾ BGRAD: Empirical parameter controlling percolation out of the bottom of the profile. This determines the bottom boundary condition only when the bottom layer is saturated. When the bottom layer is unsaturated, upward capillary flow occurs, assuming zero pressure head at the base of the profile.

Scenario	Lower boundary condition	BGRAD ¹⁾	BOTEN ²⁾	Presence of field drains	Drain depth	Drain spacing	Profile depth	max. root depth winter cereals
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²⁾ BOTEN: fixed tension at the bottom boundary of the profile

Table 7 Dummy compounds used for MACRO and PELMO simulations

Compound ID	K_{foc} ¹⁾	DT ₅₀	Freundlich exponent	plant uptake factor
	L kg⁻¹	d	-	
T1	10	10	0.9	0
T2	10	50	0.9	0
T3	10	200	0.9	0
T4	100	10	0.9	0
T5	100	50	0.9	0
T6	100	200	0.9	0
T7	1000	10	0.9	0
T8	1000	50	0.9	0
T9	1000	200	0.9	0

¹⁾ Freundlich sorption coefficient normalized to soil organic carbon content

3.1 Materials and Methods

3.1.1 PELMO simulations

The modified PELMO executable is not publicly available. For this reason the Pelmo simulations were performed by the PELMO development team (Fraunhofer IME). Except for the FOCUS gw scenario Châteaudun which had already been parameterized for PELMO, the scenarios had to be set up in PELMO from scratch by Fraunhofer IME.

Settings:

- dynamic threshold model
- length of macropores: 80 cm
- maximum root depth of crop: 80 cm
- threshold rainfall when preferential flow starts (I_c): 10 mm
- depth of drainage system: 85 cm
- potential evapotranspiration (PET): direct input
- crop coefficients for evapotranspiration K_c : mid-season: $K_c = 1.1$; late season: $K_c = 0.3$

An overview of the PELMO settings used is given in Table 8. In a first attempt, FC and WP were estimated based on the VG parameters of the MACRO scenario. However, this yielded strange (potentially numerically incorrect) results for some scenarios. Hence, the PELMO built-in pedotransfer functions for FC and WP were finally used to parameterize PELMO. This is justifiable because, given that the process descriptions of water flow are not equivalent between the two models, the parameter values do not have to be equivalent either. A list of the PELMO output variables provided by Fraunhofer is given in Table 9.

Table 8 PELMO settings used for the comparative simulations

Scenario	Macropore flow class ¹⁾	Corresponding value of f_{max}	Threshold rainfall I_c	Drain depth	Drainage efficiency	max. root depth of crop	length of macropores
Unit	-	-	mm	m	-	m	m
Châteaudun	3	0.075	10	n.a.	60 %	0.8	0.8
FOCUS D2 (Brimstone)	3	0.075	10	0.85	60 %	0.8	0.8
FOCUS D3 (Vredepeel)	1	0	10	0.85	60 %	0.8	0.8
Krusenberg	2	0.025	10	0.85	60 %	0.8	0.8
Langvad	1	0	10	0.85	60 %	0.8	0.8
Näsbygård	2	0.025	10	0.85	60 %	0.8	0.8

¹⁾ source: Skodras (personal communication)

Table 9 List of daily PELMO output variables provided by Fraunhofer IME

Variable	Unit	Description
sperc80	$\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	daily pesticide leaching flux concentration at depth of 80 cm
sperc100	$\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	daily pesticide leaching flux concentration at depth of 100 cm
spercBottom	$\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	daily pesticide leaching flux concentration at bottom of soil core
fDrainPSM	$\text{kg ha}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$	daily pesticide drainage flux
fPSMCore	$\text{kg ha}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$	daily pesticide leaching flux at bottom boundary of profile
sContPSM	kg ha^{-1}	daily total pesticide residues in core
inputWat	cm d^{-1}	daily infiltration
fevap	cm d^{-1}	daily actual evapotranspiration
fDrainWat	cm d^{-1}	daily drainflow
fWatCore	cm d^{-1}	daily percolation at bottom boundary of profile
fPercol100	cm d^{-1}	daily percolation at 1 m depth
fFlux100	cm d^{-1}	daily pesticide leaching flux at 1 m depth

3.1.2 MACRO simulations

MACRO simulations were performed by knoell. The original MACRO output variables were converted to match those of PELMO (see Table 10).

Table 10 List of daily MACRO output variables produced (units harmonized with PELMO)

Variable	Unit	Description	Calculation from original MACRO output variables
Conc100	$\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	daily leaching flux concentration in 100 cm depth	$(\text{SFLOW} + \text{SFLOWOUT})/(\text{WOUT} + \text{WFLOWOUT}) * 1000$
ConcBottom	$\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	daily leaching flux concentration at bottom of profile	$\text{SSS}/\text{WWW} * 1000$
DrainPSMflux	$\text{kg ha}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$	daily pesticide drainage flux	$\text{DSOLTOSS} * 0.24$
LeachPSMflux	$\text{kg ha}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$	daily leaching flux at the bottom of the profile	$\text{SSS} * 0.24$
LeachPSMflux100	$\text{kg ha}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$	daily leaching flux at 1 m depth	$(\text{SFLOW} + \text{SFLOWOUT}) * 0.24$ ¹⁾
Residues	kg ha^{-1}	total residues in profile	$(\text{TCAM} + \text{TPAM} + \text{TADMI} + \text{TADMA}) * 0.01$
Infiltration	cm d^{-1}	daily infiltration	$(\text{INFILMI} + \text{INFILMA}) * 2.4$
Evapot	cm d^{-1}	daily actual evapotranspiration	$\text{CETA} * 2.4$
Drainflow	cm d^{-1}	daily drainflow	$\text{SSEEP} * 2.4$
Percolation	cm d^{-1}	daily percolation beyond the bottom of the profile	$\text{WWW} * 2.4$
Percolation100	cm d^{-1}	daily percolation at 1 m depth	$(\text{WOUT} + \text{WFLOWOUT}) * 2.4$ ¹⁾

¹⁾ These are array output variables: One needs to specify a numerical layer as an argument in the output section of the .par file. The correct numerical layer corresponding to 1 m depth had to be determined for each scenario from the MACRO input file (indump.tmp), because the .par file (which is only a precursor to the indump.tmp) does not contain information about numerical layer thicknesses.

Note that for boundary condition 4 (used only for Châteaudun) there is a known numerical problem in MACRO at the bottom boundary (fixed since 2015, but still relevant for the MACRO 5.2 executable from 2010 which is still used in MACROinFOCUS). Consequently, leaching flux and leaching concentration at the bottom boundary will likely be overestimated for Châteaudun. Leaching predicted in 1 m depth is not affected.

3.1.3 Data processing

Some issues had to be dealt with when processing PELMO results:

- PELMO does not use the actual year numbers → PELMO and MACRO time series for comparison of daily outputs had to be matched by row number
- PELMO expects that always the fourth, eight etc. simulation years are leap years → Fraunhofer had to adapt the weather time series to fulfil this requirement → Length of simulation time series often differs by one day between Pelmo and MACRO, and there will sometimes be a lag of one day between MACRO and Pelmo weather time series. However, the most important time scale for the comparison is years and not days, so this problem is not crucial.

Also with MACRO some special processing was necessary:

- Specification of the modelling output in 1 m soil depth: The output layer corresponding to 1 m depth was only set for the scenario Châteaudun. For the other five scenarios, the correct output layer had to be identified by hand in the actual MACRO input file (indump.tmp), since the .par files do not contain information on numerical discretization
- Manual activation and deactivation of output variables in the input parameter files (.par) for the MACRO model
- Postprocessing of cumulative and state output variables (calculation of yearly differences)

Creation and processing of daily time series files:

- Daily time series of the outputs of both models were created in Excel (one file per model and simulation run)
- These files were subsequently used as input for the calculation of goodness-of-fit (GOF) measures (taking MACRO results as “observed” and Pelmo results as “predicted”) for several output variables and for further aggregation:
 - aggregation to yearly values
 - aggregation to mean annual values
 - calculation of the 80th percentile annual leaching flux concentration (PEC_{gw})

Calculation of goodness-of-fit (GOF) measures:

- Both daily and yearly MACRO and PELMO output tables were compared and seven GOF measures (see section 6.1 for the formulae and interpretation of each measure) were calculated for eleven output variables (with MACRO output as “observed” and PELMO output as “predicted”):
 - NSE (Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency)
 - RMSE (root mean square error)
 - PBIAS (% bias)
 - ME (mean error)
 - MAE (mean absolute error)
 - KGE (Kling-Gupta Efficiency)
 - R² (coefficient of determination) (mathematically identical to the NSE)
- The same GOF measures were also calculated for PEC_{gw}, with all simulations grouped together (n = 54)

Graphical comparison of MACRO and PELMO outputs

- Scatterplots (PELMO vs. MACRO) were created for yearly output variables
 - 54 simulations * 12 output variables = 648 plots (.png)
- Daily time series plots comparing MACRO and PELMO outputs were created for each calendar year of the 20-year evaluation period
 - Variables contained in daily resolution
 - precipitation
 - percolation (= vertical water flow) in 1 m depth

- leaching flux (= vertical substance flux) in 1 m depth
- drainflow
- pesticide drainage flux
- 54 simulations * 20 years = 1080 plots

3.2 Results and discussion

The results are presented and discussed in decreasing order of temporal aggregation, i.e., first mean annual results and the 80th percentile annual leaching flux concentration (3.2.1), subsequently annual results (3.2.2), and finally daily results (3.2.3).

3.2.1 Mean annual results and PEC_{gw}

3.2.1.1 Hydrology

Mean annual hydrological outputs and precipitation (calculated from the MACRO weather files) for the 20-year evaluation period are shown in Table 11. The following observations can be made:

- Infiltration was always slightly higher in PELMO than in MACRO. This can be explained by differences in canopy evaporation between both models. Moreover, for Näsbygard MACRO predicted some surface runoff (annual mean 7.9 mm a⁻¹; not shown), while in PELMO surface runoff was deactivated.
- Actual evapotranspiration was higher in PELMO for D2 and D3 than in MACRO, and lower for the other four scenarios.
- Mean annual drainflow volumes for D2 and D3 were twice as high in MACRO than in PELMO. Otherwise, drainflow volumes were broadly similar.
- Percolation at the bottom of the profile was always higher in PELMO than in MACRO (especially for D2 and D3), except for Langvad.
- For the comparison of percolation at 1 m depth it has to be kept in mind that in MACRO drain depth varied between scenarios (Table 6), while in PELMO it was always 85 cm (Table 8). For the undrained scenario Châteaudun and the three scenarios where drain depth in MACRO was ≤ 100 cm percolation in 1 m depth was broadly similar between PELMO and MACRO. For D3 and Langvad, where drains are considerably deeper than 1 m in MACRO, percolation in 1 m depth was substantially higher in MACRO than in PELMO.
- The mean annual water balance (calculated as precipitation – actual evapotranspiration – surface runoff – drainflow – percolation at the bottom, ignoring changes in water storage) was ≤ 3.5 mm a⁻¹ for all model/scenario combinations except for PELMO/Langvad, where the mean difference was 6.6 mm a⁻¹.
- Difference between percolation in 1 m depth and at the bottom: Since in PELMO the drains are already in 85 cm depth and cannot extract water from soil layers below drain depth, mean annual percolation at 1 m and at the bottom of the profile should be identical (or, if there are roots below 1 m, mean annual percolation at the bottom of the profile should be slightly less than at 1 m depth). However, for PELMO percolation at the bottom of the profile was always slightly higher than percolation at 1 m (up to 14 mm a⁻¹ for Châteaudun). This suggests minor problems with the numerical solution of water flow in PELMO (or with the percolation output in 1 m depth). In MACRO percolation in 1 m depth was always equal or greater than percolation at the bottom. The observed differences can be explained by removal of water by field drains. Note that in MACRO drains can remove water from both above and below drain depth (Table 2).

3.2.1.2 Solute transport

Table 12 shows mean annual solute fluxes for the six scenarios (averaged over the nine compounds), while mean annual solute fluxes for the nine compounds (averaged over the six scenarios) are shown in Table 13. For the full results please consult the file PECgw_summary_20241218.xlsx (cf. digital annex).

The main findings from averaging over the nine compounds are (Table 12):

- For the five drained scenarios, mean annual drainage fluxes (i.e. pesticide fluxes to drains) averaged over all compounds were higher in MACRO than in PELMO by a factor of 1.35 (Kruseberg) till 5.6 (D3).
- Mean annual leaching fluxes (i.e. vertical pesticide fluxes) at the bottom were consistently higher for MACRO than for PELMO, with the exception of the D2 scenario, where PELMO predicted 4.5-fold higher leaching than MACRO.
- Mean annual leaching fluxes at 1 m depth were also consistently higher for MACRO than for PELMO, with the exception of the D2 scenario, where PELMO predicted 1.7-fold higher leaching than MACRO.
- For Châteaudun in MACRO, leaching fluxes at the bottom were higher than at 1 m. This can be explained with the known numerical problem with boundary condition 4 in MACRO 5.2, which has however been fixed meanwhile (the next version of FOCUS_MACRO will include the fix).
- Since PELMO has no sinks below 1 m depth (i.e. no degradation and no substance loss to drains), the leaching fluxes in 1 m depth and at the bottom of the profile should be the same (except for substances which travel very slowly). This is more or less the case.

The main findings from averaging over the six scenarios (Table 13) are:

- For all compounds calculated leaching and drainage fluxes were greater than zero (apparent zeros in Table 13 are due to rounding).
- Drainage fluxes were always higher for MACRO than for PELMO. The ratio of predicted drainage fluxes (MACRO / PELMO) increased with increasing K_{foc} and decreasing DT_{50} . Consequently, the highest ratio of drainage fluxes was observed for compound T7 (1500), and the lowest for compound T3 (1.9). The largest differences of drainage fluxes between MACRO and PELMO were observed for the compounds T3 ($196 \text{ g ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$), T2 ($116 \text{ g ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$) and T6 ($100 \text{ g ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$); these were also the compounds for which both models simulated the highest drainage losses. Ratios and differences of predicted drainage fluxes were strongly inversely rank-correlated (Spearman $R = -0.967$).
- Leaching fluxes at the bottom of the profile were also consistently higher for MACRO than for PELMO. The highest ratio of leaching fluxes was observed for T8 (108) and the lowest for T3 (1.9). Ratios and differences of leaching fluxes at the bottom were strongly inversely rank-correlated (Spearman $R = -0.917$).
- Analogously, leaching fluxes at 1 m were always higher for MACRO than for PELMO. Again, the highest ratio of leaching fluxes was observed for T8 (83) and the lowest for T3 (2.4). Ratios and differences of leaching fluxes at 1 m between MACRO and PELMO were slightly less strongly rank-correlated (Spearman $R = -0.750$) than for the other two flux variables.

Table 11 Mean annual hydrological outputs for MACRO and PELMO and mean annual precipitation for the 20-year evaluation period

Scenario	precipitation	infiltration		actual evapotranspiration		drainflow		percolation (bottom of profile)		percolation (1 m depth)		percolation difference (1 m – bottom)	
		MACRO	PELMO	MACRO	PELMO	MACRO	PELMO	MACRO	PELMO	MACRO	PELMO	MACRO	PELMO
	cm a ⁻¹	cm a ⁻¹	cm a ⁻¹	cm a ⁻¹	cm a ⁻¹	cm a ⁻¹	cm a ⁻¹	cm a ⁻¹	cm a ⁻¹	cm a ⁻¹	cm a ⁻¹	cm a ⁻¹	cm a ⁻¹
Châteaudun	64.85	59.14	64.25	48.51	44.44	n.a.	n.a.	16.32	20.01	16.32	18.57	0.00	-1.43
D2	64.20	57.70	63.60	32.44	40.80	30.87	13.58	0.81	9.61	5.17	8.83	4.36	-0.78
D3	74.72	68.15	70.21	43.18	46.95	30.49	16.49	0.71	10.99	30.75	10.20	30.04	-0.79
Krusenberg	50.15	42.73	49.87	40.69	33.00	7.62	9.99	1.58	6.90	5.78	6.31	4.20	-0.59
Langvad	67.54	58.15	62.27	54.05	50.26	6.27	10.02	7.17	6.58	14.10	5.63	6.93	-0.95
Näsbygård	69.41	60.96	69.00	49.05	45.69	15.47	13.99	4.15	9.59	9.46	9.11	5.32	-0.48

Table 12 Mean annual solute fluxes for MACRO and PELMO for the 20-year evaluation period, aggregated by scenario over nine compounds

Scenario	pesticide drainage flux		leaching flux (bottom)		leaching flux (1 m)		leaching flux difference (1 m – bottom)	
	MACRO	PELMO	MACRO	PELMO	MACRO	PELMO	MACRO	PELMO
	kg ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹	kg ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹						
Châteaudun	n.a.	n.a.	0.167 ¹⁾	0.069	0.095	0.072	-0.0722	0.0033
D2	0.184	0.052	0.006	0.027	0.017	0.029	0.0108	0.0016
D3	0.161	0.029	0.032	0.016	0.174	0.016	0.1427	0.0005
Krusenberg	0.122	0.091	0.062	0.045	0.104	0.045	0.0420	0.0001
Langvad	0.050	0.022	0.075	0.0078	0.119	0.013	0.0443	0.0050
Näsbygård	0.130	0.086	0.064	0.048	0.093	0.047	0.0285	-0.0004

¹⁾ Known problem with bottom boundary condition 4 (constant potential). Fixed in more recent versions of MACRO.

Table 13 Mean annual solute fluxes for MACRO and PELMO for the 20-year evaluation period, aggregated by compound over six scenarios

Compound	K _{foc}	DT ₅₀	pesticide drainage flux		leaching flux (bottom)		leaching flux (1 m)		leaching flux difference (1 m – bottom)	
			MACRO	PELMO	MACRO	PELMO	MACRO	PELMO	MACRO	PELMO
	L kg ⁻¹	d	kg ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹	kg ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹						
T1	10	10	0.047	0.013	0.010	0.002	0.026	0.002	0.0159	0.0000
T2	10	50	0.211	0.095	0.130	0.060	0.205	0.059	0.0746	-0.0006
T3	10	200	0.405	0.209	0.370	0.198	0.492	0.202	0.1218	0.0037
T4	100	10	0.018	0.0001	0.0004	0.0000	0.001	0.0001	0.0009	0.0000
T5	100	50	0.058	0.008	0.007	0.002	0.015	0.003	0.0074	0.0002
T6	100	200	0.193	0.093	0.090	0.056	0.162	0.067	0.0717	0.0117
T7	1000	10	0.0005	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
T8	1000	50	0.009	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0002	0.0000	0.0002	0.0000
T9	1000	200	0.030	0.0001	0.0000	0.0000	0.0017	0.0001	0.0017	0.0001

3.2.1.3 PEC_{gw}

The target variable 80th percentile annual leaching flux concentration (“ PEC_{gw} ”) is defined as the mean of 4th and 5th highest values of the annual leaching flux concentration, for an evaluation period of 20 years (European Commission, 2014).

Scatterplots of PEC_{gw} predicted with MACRO and PELMO are shown in Figure 2, with non-logarithmic and logarithmic scales. The main results of the PEC_{gw} comparison are the following:

- For six combinations of compound and scenario, MACRO predicted a PEC_{gw} of zero, while PELMO predicted a zero PEC_{gw} for three combinations. The affected compounds were T7 and T8, and the affected scenarios D3 (three cases), Langvad (three cases), Châteaudun (two cases) and Krusenberg (one case).
- For 42 out of 54 scenario / compound combinations PEC_{gw} predicted with MACRO were higher than PEC_{gw} predicted with PELMO. The largest absolute difference observed was 1000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for Krusenberg and compound T3.
- Only for ten combinations PELMO yielded higher PEC_{gw} than MACRO; however, only for three of these there was a substantial absolute difference (120 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for D2 and compound T3; 0.29 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for Châteaudun / T9, and 0.15 for $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for Châteaudun / T4).

For more details the reader is referred to [PECgw_summary_20241218.xlsx](#) (see digital annex).

Figure 2: Scatterplot of 80th percentile annual leaching flux concentration (PEC_{gw}) simulated with PELMO (y axis) vs. MACRO (x axis). Top: non-logarithmic; bottom: logarithmic. Goodness-of-fit measures were calculated for non-logarithmic concentrations with the MACRO results as “observed” and the PELMO results as “predicted”.

3.2.2 Annual results

For the annual results the following files have been created:

- For each simulation (combination of model, scenario and compound) a table with annually aggregated results (see variables in Table 1) → 108 tables (.csv)
- An overview table (stats_yearly.csv) with seven goodness-of-fit (GOF) measures for yearly simulation results (n = 20) and all eleven output variables from the above .csv files
- For each combination of scenario, compound and annual output variable → 6 scenarios * 9 compounds * 11 output variables = 594 graphs (.png)

Table 14 Variables in annual MACRO and PELMO result tables

Variable	description	unit	remarks
Src	source (model)	n.a.	MACRO or PELMO; also included in file name
Year	calendar year	n.a.	n = 20 (warmup excluded)
Scen_KFOC_DF	concatenation of scenario, Kf _{oc} and DT ₅₀	n.a.	also included in file name
DrainPSMflux	annual pesticide drainage flux	kg ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹	
LeachPSMflux	annual leaching flux at the bottom of the profile	kg ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹	
LeachPSMflux100	annual leaching flux at 1 m depth	kg ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹	
Infiltration	annual infiltration	cm a ⁻¹	
Evapot	annual actual evapotranspiration	cm a ⁻¹	
Drainflow	annual drainflow	cm a ⁻¹	
Percolation	annual percolation beyond the bottom of the profile	cm a ⁻¹	
Percolation100	annual percolation at 1 m depth	cm a ⁻¹	
Residues	change of total residues in profile from 31/12/(n-1) till 31/12/n	kg ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹	change in residues was computed to check the solute balance
nDays	number of days of the year	n.a.	
LeachPSMfluxConc	annual leaching flux concentration at the bottom of the profile	µg L ⁻¹	
LeachPSMfluxConc100	annual leaching flux concentration at 1 m depth	µg L ⁻¹	

3.2.2.1 Hydrology

Tables 15-18 show selected GOF criteria (NSE, PBIAS, RMSE and MAE, respectively) for the yearly hydrological output variables (for a full overview see stats_yearly.csv). Figures 3-8 show scatterplots of annual drainflow and annual percolation in 1 m for PELMO vs. MACRO. The following observations can be made:

- Annual drainflow volumes matched well between PELMO and MACRO only for Näsbygard (see also Figure 8). For scenarios D2 and D3 scenario drainflow volumes simulated with PELMO are systematically lower than for MACRO (Figure 4 and Figure 5, respectively). For Krusenberg and Langvad the patterns are less clear, but on average drainflow simulated with

PELMO was substantially higher than drainflow simulated with MACRO (Figure 6 and Figure 7, respectively).

- Annual percolation at 1 m depth matched relatively well for the undrained scenario Châteaudun (Figure 3) and (with reservations) also for Krusenberg (Figure 6) and Näsbygård (Figure 8). In contrast, for D2 annual percolation at 1 m depth predicted with PELMO was consistently and substantially higher for D2 (Figure 4) compared with MACRO, which can be explained by the higher drainflow predicted with MACRO. For D3 (Figure 5) and Langvad (Figure 7) annual percolation at 1 m depth predicted with PELMO was consistently and substantially lower compared with MACRO; this can be explained by the different drain depth in both models (above 1 m in PELMO and considerably below 1 m in MACRO).

Table 15 Goodness-of-fit criterion Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) for yearly hydrological outputs (MACRO = observed; PELMO = predicted)

Scenario	Drainflow	Infiltration	Actual evapo-transpiration	Percolation at bottom	Percolation at 1 m
————— NSE ¹⁾ —————					
Châteaudun	n.a.	0.74	-0.81	0.74	0.81
D2	-7.11	0.23	-24.35	-46718.47	-22.74
D3	-2.16	0.93	-0.55	-202.25	-7.32
Krusenberg	0.51	0.36	-3.32	-45.61	0.62
Langvad	-0.01	0.68	-2.25	-0.54	-0.78
Näsbygård	0.83	0.17	-0.35	-39.61	0.55
¹⁾ A negative NSE value indicates that the mean of the observed data (here: the values simulated with MACRO) is a better predictor for the observed data than the model (here: PELMO).					

Table 16 Goodness-of-fit criterion percent bias (PBIAS) for yearly hydrological outputs (MACRO = observed; PELMO = predicted)

Scenario	Drainflow	Infiltration	Actual evapo-transpiration	Percolation at bottom	Percolation at 1 m
————— PBIAS ¹⁾ —————					
Châteaudun	n.a.	8.6	-8.4	22.6	13.8
D2	-56.0	10.2	25.8	1082.7	70.8
D3	-45.9	3.0	8.7	1439.0	-66.9
Krusenberg	31.0	16.7	-18.9	337.9	9.2
Langvad	59.7	7.1	-7.0	-8.2	-60.1
Näsbygård	-9.6	13.2	-6.8	131.4	-3.7
¹⁾ Positive values indicate overestimation by the model (here: PELMO), negative values indicate underestimation.					

Table 17 Goodness-of-fit criterion root mean squared error (RMSE) for yearly hydrological outputs (MACRO = observed; PELMO = predicted)

Scenario	Drainflow	Infiltration	Actual evapo- transpiration	Percolation at bottom	Percolation at 1 m
	————— RSME (cm a ⁻¹) ¹⁾²⁾ —————			————— RSME (cm a ⁻¹) —————	
Châteaudun	n.a.	5.28	4.59	4.59	3.95
D2	17.8	6.05	9.11	9.01	3.88
D3	14.5	2.63	5.09	11.3	21.0
Krusenberg	4.72	7.30	8.10	6.03	2.46
Langvad	5.20	4.32	4.25	2.58	9.65
Näsbygård	2.58	8.15	4.28	6.23	2.08
¹⁾ RMSE has the same unit as the respective model output variable, and its value is independent of which model results are considered as “observed” and which as “predicted”. Larger deviations get a larger weight.					
²⁾ For comparison with mean annual absolute water fluxes please consult Table 11.					

Table 18 Goodness-of-fit criterion mean absolute error (MAE) for yearly hydrological outputs (MACRO = observed; PELMO = predicted)

Scenario	Drainflow	Infiltration	Actual evapo- transpiration	Percolation at bottom	Percolation at 1 m
	————— MAE (cm a ⁻¹) ¹⁾²⁾ —————			————— MAE (cm a ⁻¹) —————	
Châteaudun	n.a.	5.11	4.07	3.79	2.97
D2	17.3	5.91	8.43	8.79	3.66
D3	14.0	2.19	4.10	10.3	20.6
Krusenberg	4.00	7.14	7.69	5.32	1.98
Langvad	4.53	4.12	3.79	2.04	8.47
Näsbygård	1.97	8.03	3.89	5.47	1.53
¹⁾ MAE has the same unit as the respective model output variable, and its value is independent of which model results are considered as “observed” and which as “predicted”. All deviations get the same weight.					
²⁾ For comparison with mean annual absolute water fluxes please consult Table 11.					

Figure 3: Scatterplot of annual percolation (cm a^{-1}) at 1 m simulated with PELMO (y axis) vs. MACRO (x axis) for scenario Châteaudun.

Figure 4: Scatterplot of drainflow (top) and annual percolation at 1 m (bottom) (cm a⁻¹) simulated with PELMO (y axis) vs. MACRO (x axis) for scenario D2 (Brimstone).

Figure 5: Scatterplot of drainflow (top) and annual percolation at 1 m (bottom) (cm a⁻¹) simulated with PELMO (y axis) vs. MACRO (x axis) for scenario D3 (Vredepeel).

Figure 6: Scatterplot of drainflow (top) and annual percolation at 1 m (bottom) simulated with PELMO (y axis) vs. MACRO (x axis) for scenario Krusenberg.

Figure 7: Scatterplot of annual drainflow (top) and annual percolation at 1 m (bottom) simulated with PELMO (y axis) vs. MACRO (x axis) for scenario Langvad.

Figure 8: Scatterplot of annual drainflow (top) and annual percolation at 1 m (bottom) simulated with PELMO (y axis) vs. MACRO (x axis) for scenario Näsbygård.

3.2.2.2 Solute transport

Tables 19-24 show selected GOF criteria (NSE and PBIAS) for the yearly solute transport output variables (for a full overview of all individual runs and GOF measures see stats_yearly.csv). In Tables 19-21 the annual fluxes and concentrations are grouped by scenario (and thus averaged over the nine compounds), while in Tables 22-24 the results are grouped by compound (and averaged over the six scenarios). For the results grouped by scenario, the main observations can be summarized as follows:

- The Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) aggregated by scenario was negative for all scenarios and the five solute transport outputs (Table 19). This means that the PELMO predictions matched the annual MACRO results less well than the mean of the annual MACRO result did. The most negative NSE values (the more negative the NSE, the stronger the deviation from the 1:1 line) were found for Châteaudun and Krusenberg). However, given that the NSE can reach minus infinity, averaging the NSE over different scenarios or compounds is problematic, because one strongly negative value can mask the others.
- Percent bias (PBIAS) aggregated by scenario also yielded strong deviations between PELMO and MACRO (Table 20). Again, the strongest deviations were found for Châteaudun and Krusenberg. Note, however, that PBIAS does not give information about the match of the annual pattern, because the differences are just summed up over the 20 years (eq. A3). Moreover, since PBIAS can approach both plus and minus infinity averaging over PBIAS is also problematic.
- The root mean square error (RMSE) aggregated by scenario showed in general large deviations for the annual leaching flux concentrations in both at the bottom and in 1 m depth, especially for Krusenberg.

Table 19 Goodness-of-fit criterion Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) for yearly solute transport outputs (MACRO = observed; PELMO = predicted), aggregated by scenario over nine compounds

Scenario	annual pesticide drainage flux	annual leaching flux (bottom)	annual leaching flux (1 m)	annual leaching flux conc. (bottom)	annual leaching flux conc. (1 m)
	-----NSE ¹⁾ -----				
Châteaudun	n.a.	-54.21	-4.70E+08	-8.28	-1.02E+08
D2	-7.19	-100.63	-27.00	-9.86	-30.57
D3	-64.26	-3.94	-4.97	-0.67	-10.23
Krusenberg	-1.87E+38	-2.75E+06	-32204.24	-0.10	-1254.46
Langvad	-0.48	-2.40	-1.44	-2.37	-9.89
Näsbygård	-0.75	-1.27	-1.02	-31.74	-3.79

¹⁾ A negative NSE values indicate that the mean of the observed data (here: the values simulated with MACRO) values is a better predictor than the model (here: PELMO).

Table 20 Goodness-of-fit criterion percent bias (PBIAS) for yearly solute transport outputs (MACRO = observed; PELMO = predicted), aggregated by scenario over nine compounds

Scenario	annual pesticide drainage flux	annual leaching flux (bottom)	annual leaching flux (1 m)	annual leaching flux conc. (bottom)	annual leaching flux conc. (1 m)
————— PBIAS ¹⁾ —————					
Châteaudun	n.a.	312.6	2.1E+06	92.4	9.5E+05
D2	-84.5	45.9	-34.1	-87.7	-61.3
D3	616.3	-56.1	-92.8	-100.0	-78.7
Krusenberg	1.1E+21	28486.8	14569.5	-118.6	4215.5
Langvad	-77.8	-97.0	-95.8	-96.6	-89.9
Näsbygård	-66.9	-63.9	-70.8	-84.3	-71.2
¹⁾ Positive values indicate overestimation by the model (here: PELMO), negative values indicate underestimation.					

Table 21 Goodness-of-fit criterion percent bias (RMSE) for yearly solute transport outputs (MACRO = observed; PELMO = predicted), aggregated by scenario over nine compounds

Scenario	annual pesticide drainage flux	annual leaching flux (bottom)	annual leaching flux (1 m)	annual leaching flux conc. (bottom)	annual leaching flux conc. (1 m)
————— RMSE (kg ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹) ¹⁾ —————			————— RMSE (µg L ⁻¹) —————		
Châteaudun	n.a.	0.114	0.042	132.84	26.28
D2	0.142	0.024	0.022	49.78	24.58
D3	0.142	0.023	0.165	1.3E+05	43.00
Krusenberg	0.100	0.028	0.079	3.2E+05	763.57
Langvad	0.051	0.073	0.122	114.43	67.49
Näsbygård	0.066	0.021	0.053	107.00	50.96
¹⁾ RMSE has the same unit as the respective model output variable.					

For the results grouped by compound, the main observations can be summarized as follows:

- NSE aggregated by compound (Table 22) was also negative throughout. However, the most negative values were found for the three strongly sorbing compounds with K_{foc} 1000 L kg⁻¹.
- PBIAS was also highest for the three compounds with $K_{foc} = 1000$ L kg⁻¹, where simulated fluxes were generally low.
- RMSE of the annual leaching flux concentration (both at the bottom and at 1 m depth) was highest for the compounds with the highest predicted leaching: T2, T3, T5 and T6

Table 22 Goodness-of-fit criterion Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) for yearly solute transport outputs (MACRO = observed; PELMO = predicted), aggregated by compound over six scenarios

Compound	K _{foc}	DT ₅₀	annual pesticide drainage flux	annual leaching flux (bottom)	annual leaching flux (1 m)	annual leaching flux conc. (bottom)	annual leaching flux conc. (1 m)
	L kg ⁻¹	d	----- NSE ^{1) 2)} -----				
T1	10	10	-1.87	-8.56	-2.02	-12.95	-3.06
T2	10	50	-2.56	-40.13	-3.64	-32.46	-8.83
T3	10	200	-1.82	-105.42	-31.90	-15.71	-28.06
T4	100	10	-17.33	-55.42	-72.70	-9.16	-99.03
T5	100	50	-3.33	-1.97	-2.98	-2.39	-5.16
T6	100	200	-3.20	-2.33	-1.91	-1.15	-15.85
T7	1000	10	-4.22E+38	-0.20	-0.17	-0.24	-0.20
T8	1000	50	-90319.56	-5.49E+06	-64411.36	-0.49	-2513.70
T9	1000	200	-72.92	-0.51	-5.48E+08	-0.63	-1.19E+08
¹⁾ A negative NSE value indicates that the mean of the observed data (here: the values simulated with MACRO) is a better predictor than the model (here: PELMO).							
²⁾ In contrast to Table 13, where mean annual solute fluxes were averaged over the scenarios, here NSE of annual fluxes was averaged over the scenarios. However, the averaging of NSE is very sensitive to outliers.							

Table 23 Goodness-of-fit criterion percent bias (PBIAS) for yearly solute transport outputs (MACRO = observed; PELMO = predicted), aggregated by compound over six scenarios

Compound	K _{foc}	DT ₅₀	annual pesticide drainage flux	annual leaching flux (bottom)	annual leaching flux (1 m)	annual leaching flux conc. (bottom)	annual leaching flux conc. (1 m)
	L kg ⁻¹	d	----- PBIAS (%) ¹⁾²⁾ -----				
T1	10	10	-55.4	-73.4	-76.7	-90.9	-64.7
T2	10	50	-51.4	-5.8	-44.4	-83.9	-47.9
T3	10	200	-45.5	62.7	-12.1	-78.1	79.9
T4	100	10	2.1	301.8	685.2	71.3	874.8
T5	100	50	-73.6	-71.1	-76.7	-93.6	-73.7
T6	100	200	-46.6	-15.8	-50.0	-86.0	-42.3
T7	1000	10	2.5E+21	-100.0	-92.5	-100.0	-97.1
T8	1000	50	29593.7	56935.8	29166.9	-136.9	8271.0
T9	1000	200	825.4	-59.7	2.5E+06	-100.1	1.1E+06
¹⁾ Positive values indicate overestimation by the model (here: PELMO), negative values underestimation.							
²⁾ In contrast to Table 13, where mean annual solute fluxes were averaged over the scenarios, here PBIAS of annual fluxes was averaged over the scenarios. However, the averaging of PBIAS is very sensitive to outliers.							

Table 24 Goodness-of-fit criterion percent bias (RMSE) for yearly solute transport outputs (MACRO = observed; PELMO = predicted), aggregated by compound over six scenarios

Compound	K_{foc}	DT_{50}	annual pesticide drainage flux	annual leaching flux (bottom)	annual leaching flux (1 m)	annual leaching flux conc. (bottom)	annual leaching flux conc. (1 m)
	$L\ kg^{-1}$	d	———— RMSE ($kg\ ha^{-1}\ a^{-1}$) ¹⁾ ————			———— RMSE ($\mu g\ L^{-1}$) ————	
T1	10	10	0.045	9.2E-03	0.029	19428.92	33.54
T2	10	50	0.287	0.261	0.386	3.4E+05	939.08
T3	10	200	0.159	0.092	0.174	1.6E+05	207.70
T4	100	10	0.020	5.3E-04	1.8E-03	36.27	2.39
T5	100	50	0.142	0.056	0.115	1.4E+05	257.05
T6	100	200	0.057	6.1E-03	0.015	1.3E+04	20.87
T7	1000	10	7.4E-04	3.9E-11	4.4E-08	7.7E-08	9.1E-05
T8	1000	50	0.031	4.5E-05	2.0E-03	2.12	2.86
T9	1000	200	0.010	2.1E-06	2.0E-04	0.01	0.34

¹⁾ RMSE has the same unit as the respective model output variable

The analysis of Tables 19-24 showed that averaging of GOF measures by scenarios or compounds may lead to too much loss of information. However, is it not possible here to discuss GOF measures for all simulations individually. To give a further impression of the overall match of the annual flux and concentration patterns, we extracted the numbers of simulations with positive NSE (i.e. where PELMO matches the MACRO results better than the mean of the MACRO results does):

- annual pesticide drainage flux: n = 9 (out of 45)
- annual leaching flux at the bottom: n = 5 (out of 54)
- annual leaching flux at 1 m depth: n = 8 (out of 54)
- annual leaching flux concentration at the bottom: 0 (out of 54)
- annual leaching flux concentration at 1 m depth: 6 (out of 54)

For a few simulations PELMO predicted on average higher annual fluxes or leaching flux concentrations than MACRO (PBIAS > 0):

- annual pesticide drainage flux: n = 6 (out of 45)
 - however, in five out of these six cases (except T1/Krusenberg) predicted drainage fluxes were very low for both models
- annual leaching flux at the bottom: n = 6 (out of 54)
- annual leaching flux at 1 m depth: n = 5 (out of 54)
- annual leaching flux concentration at the bottom: 1 (out of 54)
- annual leaching flux concentration at 1 m depth: 8 (out of 54)

For instance, for compound T9 ($K_{foc} = 1000\ L\ kg^{-1}$, $DT_{50} = 200\ d$) and scenarios Châteaudun and Krusenberg PELMO predicted higher annual leaching flux concentrations at 1 m than MACRO (Figure 9). This can probably be explained by the fact that PELMO does not simulate any sorption in the macropores or in the mixing layer. Hence, even strongly sorbing compounds can be transferred to 80 cm depth (the end of the macropores) instantaneously.

Figure 9: Scatterplot of annual leaching flux conc. at 1 m simulated with PELMO (y axis) vs. MACRO (x axis) for Châteaudun (top) and Krusenberg (bottom) and compound T9 ($K_{\text{foc}} = 1000 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$, $\text{DT}_{50} = 200 \text{ d}$)

Figures 10-15 show scatterplots of annual pesticide drainage fluxes, leaching fluxes in 1 m depth and annual leaching flux concentrations for PELMO vs. MACRO for all six scenarios and one example compound (T2; $K_{foc} = 10 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$, $DT_{50} = 50 \text{ d}$). This compound was selected for discussion because of the good visibility of the data points. Scatterplots for the other compounds and the remaining solute output variables (annual leaching flux at the bottom of the profile, annual leaching flux concentration at the bottom, annual change of residues) can be found in the digital annex.

- For the undrained scenario Châteaudun (Figure 10), the annual leaching flux in 1 m depth calculated by MACRO was comparatively well matched by PELMO (NSE = 0.429) except for some underestimation (PBIAS = - 30 %). For the annual leaching flux concentration NSE was close to zero, i.e. the prediction (PELMO) was just as good as the mean of the “observed” data (MACRO).
- For scenario D2 (Figure 11), annual drainage fluxes predicted with PELMO were systematically lower than for MACRO, while the opposite was the case for the leaching flux in 1 m depth. Pesticide leaching concentrations in 1 m depth predicted with PELMO were almost unbiased (PBIAS = - 5 %), but rather widely scattered around the 1:1 line.
- For scenario D3 (Figure 12) PELMO clearly underestimated all three variables compared with MACRO. Note that for this scenario no macropore flow was simulated by PELMO (cf. Table 8). On the other hand, D3 is a sandy soil and not particularly prone to macropore flow.
- For scenario Krusenberg (Figure 13) annual drainage flux was moderately well matched by PELMO, while leaching flux and leaching flux concentrations in 1 m depth were systematically underestimated.
- For scenario Langvad (Figure 14) annual drainflow was underestimated by PELMO most of the time, while annual leaching flux and leaching flux concentration in 1 m depth were strongly underestimated. This can be partly explained by the different drain depths simulated for Langvad (85 cm in PELMO vs. 1.3 m in MACRO). Moreover, the choice of mcp class 1 (no macropore flow simulated) for PELMO (Table 8) was probably not appropriate for Langvad.
- For scenario Näsbygard (Figure 15) annual drainage flux was moderately underestimated by PELMO (PBIAS = -30 %), while annual leaching flux and leaching flux concentration in 1 m depth were on averaged underestimated by a factor of 2.

Figure 10: Scatterplot of annual leaching flux at 1 m (top) and annual leaching flux conc. at 1 m (bottom) simulated with PELMO (y axis) vs. MACRO (x axis) for Châteaudun and compound T2 ($K_{foc} = 10 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$, $DT_{50} = 50 \text{ d}$).

Figure 11: Scatterplot of annual drainage flux (top), annual leaching flux at 1 m (middle) and annual leaching flux conc. at 1 m (bottom) simulated with PELMO (y axis) vs. MACRO (x axis) for D2 and compound T2 ($K_{foc} = 10 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$, $DT_{50} = 50 \text{ d}$).

Figure 12: Scatterplot of annual drainage flux (top), annual leaching flux at 1 m (middle) and annual leaching flux conc. at 1 m (bottom) simulated with PELMO (y axis) vs. MACRO (x axis) for D3 and compound T2 ($K_{\text{foc}} = 10 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$, $\text{DT}_{50} = 50 \text{ d}$).

Figure 13: Scatterplot of annual drainage flux (top), annual leaching flux at 1 m (middle) and annual leaching flux conc. at 1 m (bottom) simulated with PELMO (y axis) vs. MACRO (x axis) for Krusenberg and compound T2 ($K_{foc} = 10 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$, $DT_{50} = 50 \text{ d}$).

Figure 14: Scatterplot of annual drainage flux (top), annual leaching flux at 1 m (middle) and annual leaching flux conc. at 1 m (bottom) simulated with PELMO (y axis) vs. MACRO (x axis) for Langvad and compound T2 ($K_{foc} = 10 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$, $DT_{50} = 50 \text{ d}$).

Figure 15: Scatterplot of annual drainage flux (top), annual leaching flux at 1 m (middle) and annual leaching flux conc. at 1 m (bottom) simulated with PELMO (y axis) vs. MACRO (x axis) for Näsbygård and compound T2 ($K_{foc} = 10 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$, $DT_{50} = 50 \text{ d}$).

3.2.3 Daily results

A table with GOF measures for the daily time series has been produced (stats_daily.csv; see digital annex). However, this table is not discussed here, because i) the relevant time scale for leaching assessments is years and not days, and ii) the leap year problem in PELMO can cause a shift of one day for prolonged periods of time, which affects several GOF measures negatively (notably NSE, RMSE and MAE). All daily output time series (from both MACRO and PELMO) can be found in the digital annex.

For the scenarios Langvad and D3 (which were simulated without macropore flow) often a ratio of exact 0.9 between infiltration and rainfall was observed in the PELMO output. It remains to be clarified whether this is a bug in the output variable infiltration (inputWat) or something different.

Figures 16-20 show six examples (one for each scenario, substance T2 ($K_{foc} = 10 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$, $DT_{50} = 50 \text{ d}$), one selected calendar year) from the 1080 created daily time series plots.

For the undrained scenario Châteaudun (Figure 16) percolation and leaching for T2 at 1 m depth were substantially more peaky for PELMO than for MACRO. The general timing was similar, except that percolation and leaching peaks predicted with PELMO arrived slightly earlier due to instantaneous macropore flow.

For the heavy clay scenario D2 (Figure 17) with strong macropore flow in MACRO timing was very similar for the two models. The main difference between the two models was the magnitude of both pathways (leaching and drainflow): MACRO predicted larger drainflow and drainage flux than PELMO, while PELMO predicted higher percolation and leaching flux.

For the sandy drainage scenario D3 (Figure 18) with only little macropore flow in MACRO (and no macropore flow in PELMO) both timing and peakiness were fundamentally different between the two

models. This is probably due to the site hydrology of D3 (permanent shallow groundwater with drains at the bottom of the profile) which is not represented at all in PELMO.

For the Swedish leaching scenario Krusenberg (Figure 19) (which features a sharp textural boundary at 50 cm depth with loamy sand over heavy clay) the predicted time series were considerably more peaky for PELMO than for MACRO. While PELMO reacted almost instantaneously to rainfall events outside the summer period, the reaction of MACRO was rather dampened (time lag of about two weeks + long recession).

Also for the Danish leaching scenario Langvad (Figure 20) PELMO yielded peakier time series than MACRO, although the scenario was simulated without macropore flow in PELMO (Table 8). Simulated leaching in 1 m depth was much higher for MACRO than for PELMO. The large observed difference between MACRO and PELMO with respect to the start of drainage can be partly explained by the different drain depths (0.85 m in PELMO vs. 1.3 m in MACRO). For the loamy Swedish leaching scenario Näsbygard (Figure 21) PELMO yielded again more peaky time series than MACRO, although the timing of peaks was similar.

Figure 16: Example time series plot for scenario Châteaudun, substance T2 ($K_{foc} = 10 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$, $DT_{50} = 50 \text{ d}$) and year 1980. The plot contains the following variables in daily resolution: precipitation (top), percolation and leaching flux at 1 m depth (both PELMO and MACRO; middle), drainflow and pesticide drainage flux (both PELMO and MACRO; bottom). The latter two variables are always zero since Châteaudun is undrained.

Figure 17: Example time series plot for scenario D2, substance T2 ($K_{foc} = 10 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$, $DT_{50} = 50 \text{ d}$) and year 1983. The plot contains the following variables in daily resolution: precipitation (top), percolation and leaching flux at 1 m depth (both PELMO and MACRO; middle)), drainflow and pesticide drainage flux (both PELMO and MACRO; bottom).

Figure 18: Example time series plot for scenario D3, substance T2 ($K_{foc} = 10 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$, $DT_{50} = 50 \text{ d}$) and year 1979. The plot contains the following variables in daily resolution: precipitation (top), percolation and leaching flux at 1 m depth (both PELMO and MACRO; middle), drainflow and pesticide drainage flux (both PELMO and MACRO; bottom).

Figure 19: Example time series plot for scenario Krusenberg, substance T2 ($K_{foc} = 10 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$, $DT_{50} = 50 \text{ d}$) and year 1976. The plot contains the following variables in daily resolution: precipitation (top), percolation and leaching flux at 1 m depth (both PELMO and MACRO; middle), drainflow and pesticide drainage flux (both PELMO and MACRO; bottom).

Figure 20: Example time series plot for scenario Langvad, substance T2 ($K_{foc} = 10 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$, $DT_{50} = 50 \text{ d}$) and year 1978. The plot contains the following variables in daily resolution: precipitation (top), percolation and leaching flux at 1 m depth (both PELMO and MACRO; middle), drainflow and pesticide drainage flux (both PELMO and MACRO; bottom).

Figure 21: Example time series plot for scenario Näsbygard, substance T2 ($K_{foc} = 10 \text{ L kg}^{-1}$, $DT_{50} = 50 \text{ d}$) and year 1989. The plot contains the following variables in daily resolution: precipitation (top), percolation and leaching flux at 1 m depth (both PELMO and MACRO; middle), drainflow and pesticide drainage flux (both PELMO and MACRO; bottom).

4 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

In this study the process description of MACRO and the macropore version of PELMO have been compared, and a set of 54 comparative simulations (6 regulatory scenarios * 9 dummy compounds) has been conducted for an evaluation period of 20 years. Process descriptions for macropore flow were found to be fundamentally different between both models, which would make the transfer of scenario parameters from one model to the other almost impossible. The most important findings from the comparative simulations were:

- Hydrology
 - The comparability of the hydrology between the two models was hampered by several issues:
 - drain depth was fixed at the same value in PELMO for all scenarios and was always different from the drain depth in the MACRO parameterization of the regulatory scenario
 - a fixed drainage efficiency of 60 % was assumed in the PELMO simulations, regardless of soil properties
 - PELMO cannot simulate an impermeable or slowly permeable lower boundary, which was present in 5 out of 6 MACRO scenarios, and thus neither a permanent or temporary shallow water table
 - Only for Näsbygård the annual drainflow volumes matched well between PELMO and MACRO.
 - Only for the undrained scenario Châteaudun and (with reservations) for Krusenberg and Näsbygård the annual percolation at 1 m depth matched relatively well.
- Solutes:
 - For the five drained scenarios, mean annual drainage fluxes averaged over all compounds were higher in MACRO than in PELMO by a factor of 1.35 till 5.6.
 - On a scenario basis, mean annual leaching fluxes (both at 1 m depth and at the bottom) were consistently higher for MACRO than for PELMO, with the exception of the D2 scenario where the main export pathway is drainage.
 - With regard to the 80th percentile annual leaching flux concentration (PEC_{gw}),
 - For 42 out of 54 scenario-compound-combinations PEC_{gw} predicted with MACRO were higher than PEC_{gw} predicted with PELMO (up to 1000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)
 - Only for 10 combinations PELMO yielded higher PEC_{gw} than MACRO; however, only in three of these there was a substantial absolute difference
 - Annual fluxes and leaching flux concentrations generally badly matched between PELMO and MACRO

Before drawing a conclusion on the question how well PELMO is able to reproduce water flow and solute transport patterns predicted by MACRO for regulatory leaching and drainage scenarios, further test simulations would be necessary with scenario-specific drain depth and drainage efficiency in PELMO. Moreover, the current parameterization method for macropore flow in PELMO (notably the flowchart for the macropore class) needs further testing and validation. New tests should also include simulations with i) the standard version of PELMO and ii) the macropore version of PELMO with macropore class 1 (no macropore flow) as control.

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6 ANNEX

6.1 Goodness-of-fit measures

A number of goodness-of-fit (GOF) measures were calculated (eqs. A1-A6; Table A 1), with the MACRO results as “observed” and the PELMO results as “predicted” values.

$$NSE = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - P_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O})^2} \quad (\text{eq. A1})$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - P_i)^2}{n}} \quad (\text{eq. A2})$$

$$PBIAS = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - O_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i)} 100\% \quad (\text{eq. A3})$$

$$ME = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - O_i)}{n} \quad (\text{eq. A4})$$

$$MAE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |P_i - O_i|}{n} \quad (\text{eq. A5})$$

$$KGE = 1 - \sqrt{(r - 1)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_p}{\sigma_o} - 1\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\mu_p}{\mu_o} - 1\right)^2} \quad (\text{eq. A6})$$

where O_i = observed value of the i^{th} data point, P_i = predicted value for the i^{th} data point, \bar{O} is the mean of the observed data, n = number of data points, σ = standard deviation and μ = arithmetic mean.

Further explanations of the GOF measures are given in Table A 1.

If the perspective were to be switched (i.e. PELMO results were treated as “observed” and MACRO results as “predicted”, the values of NSE, PBIAS, KGE would change, potentially dramatically. RMSE and MAE would not change, and ME would only change the sign.

Table A 1 Goodness-of-fit measures calculated for comparison of PELMO and MACRO results

GOF measure	description	reference	unit	min value	max value	optimum value	remarks
ME	mean error			- inf	+ inf	0	measure of absolute bias
MAE	mean absolute error	e.g. Legates and McCabe (1999)	same unit as compared variables	0	+ inf	0	measure of mean deviation from 1:1 line
RMSE	root mean square error	e.g. Hyndman and Koehler (2006)		0	+ inf	0	measure of deviation from 1:1 line, with larger deviations getting a larger weight
PBIAS	percent bias	e.g. Moriasi et al. (2007)	%	- inf	+ inf	0	measure of relative bias; note that there are two different

GOF measure	description	reference	unit	min value	max value	optimum value	remarks
							definitions with opposite signs
NSE	Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency	Nash and Sutcliffe (1970)	n.a.	- inf	1	1	ratio of mean square error to variance in the observed data, subtracted from unity
KGE	Kling-Gupta Efficiency	Gupta et al. (2009)		- inf	1	1	measure composed of three components: correlation, variability and bias
R ²	coefficient of determination	e.g. Reichenberger et al. (2019)		- inf	1	1	ratio of explained variance to total variance; mathematically identical to NSE; only identical to the squared correlation coefficient r ² in case of linear regression

6.2 Original MACRO output variables

The original output variables of the 54 MACRO simulations are listed in Table A 2. Note that flux output variables in MACRO are always expressed per hour, irrespective of the output time step.

Table A 2 Goodness-of-fit measures calculated for comparison of PELMO and MACRO results

Variable	description	unit	remarks
CCET	Accumulated actual evapotranspiration	mm	
CETA	Actual evapotranspiration rate	mm h ⁻¹	
DSOLTOSS	Solute flow rate to tile drains, including both micro- and macropores.	mg m ⁻² h ⁻¹	
EPOT	Potential evapotranspiration rate	mm h ⁻¹	
ETA	Actual transpiration rate	mm h ⁻¹	
GSRAT	Water flow to secondary drainage system	mm h ⁻¹	only relevant for BOUNDARY = 3 (water table in the profile)
INFILMA	Infiltration rate (macropores)	mm h ⁻¹	
INFILMI	Infiltration rate (micropores)	mm h ⁻¹	
PRECIRA	Accumulated precipitation*RAINCO + Irrigation	mm	corrected precipitation
PRECIRR	Precipitation*RAINCO + Irrigation rate	mm h ⁻¹	
PSOIL	Potential soil evaporation rate	mm h ⁻¹	
SFLOW_99-100_100	Solute flow rate out of layer (micropores)	mg m ⁻² h ⁻¹	layered output variables; output for the layer with the lower limit closest to 1 m depth
SFLOWOUT_99-100_100	Solute flow rate out of layer (macropores)	mg m ⁻² h ⁻¹	
SRUNOFF	Surface runoff	mm h ⁻¹	

Variable	description	unit	remarks
SSEEP	Water flow to primary drainage system (from both macro- and micropores)	mm h ⁻¹	
SSRAT	Solute flux to secondary drain system (from both macro- and micropores)	mg m ⁻² h ⁻¹	
SSS	Solute leaching rate (total) - This is the loss rate of solute out of the bottom of the soilprofile (including both micro- and macropores).	mg m ⁻² h ⁻¹	
TADMA	Solute storage in profile (macropores only, solid phase)	mg m ⁻²	
TADMI	Solute storage in profile (micropores only, solid phase)	mg m ⁻²	
TCAM	Solute storage in profile (macropores only, liquid phase)	mg m ⁻²	
TDEG	Accumulated amount of solute degraded in soil	mg m ⁻²	
TFLOWOUT	Accumulated percolation (total) - This is the accumulated total flow out of the bottom layer of the profile (i.e. including macropores and micropores).	mm	
TPAM	Solute storage in profile (micropores only, liquid phase)	mg m ⁻²	
TRUNOFF	Accumulated surface runoff	mm	
TSOUT	Accumulated solute leaching out of the bottom of the profile (both micro- and macropores)	mg m ⁻²	
TSRUN	Accumulated amount of solute lost in surface runoff	mg m ⁻²	
TSTOREMA	Water storage in macropores (profile) - This is the total profile storage of water in the macropores.	mm	
TSTOREMI	Water storage in micropores (profile) - This is the total profile storage of water in the micropores.	mm	
TUPT	Accumulated solute uptake by crop	mg m ⁻²	
WETACT	Actual canopy evaporation rate	mm h ⁻¹	
WFLOWOUT_99-100_100	Water flow rate out of layer (macropores)	mm h ⁻¹	layered output variables; output for the layer with the lower limit closest to 1 m depth
WOUT_99-100_100	Water flow rate out of layer (micropores)	mm h ⁻¹	
WWW	Percolation (total) - This is the total flow out of the bottom layer of the profile (i.e. including both macropores and micropores).	mm h ⁻¹	

6.3 List of delivered results (digital annex)

List of delivered results (122289_eval_20250106.zip; sent via Cryptshare on 06/02/2025):

Folder Daily_2025-01-06 contains:

- 1) Subfolder daily_csv: Daily MACRO and Pelmo results (.csv) in harmonized format; file names are a concatenation of model, scenario, K_{foc} and DT_{50} (e.g. MACRO_D2_Kfoc100_dt200.csv); 108 .csv files
- 2) Documentation of the variables in the above files: Variables_daily_timeseries_MACRO_PELMO.xlsx
- 3) GOF measures for daily time series: stats_daily.csv
- 4) Subfolder timeseries_plots: Daily time series plots of MACRO and PELMO draining and leaching outputs, separately for each calendar year (6 scenarios * 9 compounds * 20 years = 1080 graphs (.png))

Folder Annual_2025-01-06 contains:

- 1) Subfolder annual_csv: Annually aggregated MACRO and Pelmo results (.csv) in harmonized format; file names are a concatenation of model, scenario, K_{foc} and DT_{50} (e.g. MACRO_D2_Kfoc100_dt200_yearly.csv); 108 .csv files
- 2) Documentation of the variables in the above files: Variables_annual_results_MACRO_Pelmo.xlsx
- 3) GOF measures for annual results: stats_yearly_20241104.xlsx
- 4) Subfolder annual_plots: Scatterplots (MACRO vs. PELMO) of annual output variables (6 scenarios * 9 compounds * 12 output variables = 648 graphs (.png))

Folder MACRO_out_2024-04-19 contains:

- 1) Subfolder out_bin: original binary MACRO output files (.bin); file names contain the compound ID (T1-T9) and the first letters of the scenario
- 2) Subfolder out_csv: Daily output time series of MACRO (.csv) as extracted from the original output; file names contain model, scenario, K_{foc} and DT_{50} (e.g. MACRO_D2_Kfoc100_dt200.csv)
- 3) Subfolder par_files: contains the precursor input files for MACRO (.par); same nomenclature as for the .bin files
- 4) Subfolder meteo: contains the meteorological driving data for the MACRO simulations (.bin)

Folder PELMO_out_2024-10-30 contains only one file: PELMO_time_series_20241030.xlsx (original PELMO output as received from Fraunhofer)

Folder “PECgw_summary” contains:

- 1) PECgw_summary_20241218.xlsx:
This file contains “global” results:
 - Overall mean leaching flux concentration over 20 years at 1 m depth
 - Overall mean flux concentration over 20 years at the bottom
 - 80th percentile annual leaching flux concentration (“PEC_{gw}”)
 - Mean annual water and solute fluxes
- 2) Explanation of the variables in the above file: Variables_PECgw_summary_20241218.xlsx
- 3) PECgw_80th_perc_GOF.csv: goodness-of-fit (GOF) measures for PEC_{gw} (n = 54)
- 4) PECgw_80th_perc_GOF_orig.png: scatterplot of PEC_{gw} (n = 54)
- 5) log10_PECgw_80th_perc_GOF.png: scatterplot of log₁₀(PEC_{gw}); however, the GOF measures still refer to non-logarithmic values